

Emotion Recognition Based on Facial Expression By Inference Kalman Filter

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Abstract

This paper is aimed at producing a simple mechanism that detects emotion on a person's face from the facial expression as recognised in real-time, the main purpose is to be able to apply a real control panel for Kalman Filter Model (KLM) by tracking the error in frequency while tracing the mood change and detecting error that minimises false positive cases. The initial stage is designed in such a way it automatically detects and tracks the facial feature points with cascaded markers that keep track of the face even while the subject tilts in different directions and positions. This approach is very simple in computer vision applications for most network surveillance and automotive safety. The tracking process uses three modules: (1) face detection (2) feature identification (3) face tracking and detection. The module is signalised as a vision cascade object detector system to detect and locate a face from a video sequence; the detector object uses the KLM inference that trains the classification model for detection. The module can also be used to track moving objects with distinct features. The originality of the process is that all vision point tracker works as a window-based control system. The system is also embedded with error detection and tracking points, with a frequency of 10Hz from every facial angle, and can be used to track even the most subtle point of a blurred image at an estimated geometric transform.

Keywords: Inference Kalman filter, Tracking point, Tracing mood, Facial expression, Subtle point, Vision cascade object detector

Facial Expression By Inference Kalman Filter

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1 INTRODUCTION

Research [1, 2, 3, 4, 5] in recent years has seen the enhancement of every aspect of the interaction between humans and machines, especially in the field of human expression and emotion recognition. Some work [6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 14, 15], has used robust systems by combing different techniques from computer vision and pattern recognition.

Part of the work is dividing the system into four different modules image pre-processing, feature extraction, feature selection, and forward selection. Most classification is done using functions like support vector machine (SVM), on Radboud faces databases (RFD). The main aim is to attain a higher possible classification rate for all facial expressions in the database and achieve 75.8% recognition accuracy in the training set.

The method of training does not necessarily have to be robust but also has a simple standard technique that can do the dynamic job of feature selection by simple point identification in the most subtle of expressions. Since the face is delicate, a slight expression might not be detected even with robust search algorithms. Facial expression recognition is very important and very useful, especially in an Artificial intelligence (AI) program like a custom analytic tool for evaluators, where an expert needs to understand the facial features of a customer without subjective views. Since the tool needs to capture the conscious expressions of the user, we can have the chance to predict users' moods for product optimisation. Different facial expressions are always reflected in the human face because it sometimes shows the inner feelings of the person, such feelings could be sadness, happiness, and neutral mood, these emotions are used in the computer vision system as an input to recognise the facial expression and can also be used as an additional attribute that characterises certain aspects of a person's face that uniquely identify the person. Most facial expression systems can typically recognise a person based on the five most widely used expressions, such as sad, happy, anger, disgust, and fear.

The work of ([16, 17]), studies the effects of occluding six (6) prototypic facial expressions (Figure 1) on recognising facial expressions. In their paper, they applied three approaches for feature extraction using the Gabor feature by Geometric displacement vectors extracted using the Candide track and DNMF algorithm. A multi-class SVM was implemented and supported multi-layer perception on the JAFFE databases. The recognition was detected as having a low error rate of 0.12% and an authentic way for feature and face recognition [18, 19, 20, 21, 22].

Generally speaking, every face emotion recognition system must perform four basic steps before classifying the expression into a particular emotion this includes image pre-processing, feature extraction, feature selection, and expression recognition before an inference system is used to classify and test the expressions in the input facial expression. This paper uses a simple standard KLM for filter and feature selection on a real-time video sequence to automatically detect facial features and default expression, the tracking accuracy is also measured and compared with the Viola-Jones algorithm as a signalised control system. Error tracking and feature prediction are based on the equation in Figure 2. The following section discusses the methods and results obtained from the point track.

2 METHOD

The method adopted here is based on a dynamic window-controlled KLM with room for the input of video sequences, either in real-time or served in the archives. The

points can be identified by activating the radio buttons and using a vision point tracker control object to track the faces in a video frame. The point tracker attempts to track each point in the previous frame by finding the corresponding point in the current frame. The estimated geometric Transform (EGT) function (Figure 3) is used to estimate the translation, scale, and rotation between the previous points and the new points; the rapid transformation is applied to the cascaded bounding box that surrounds the face. Each tracking point from frame to frame uses the EGT function to estimate the motion of the face. They can also be done for multiple faces detected in a single video screening and multiple video sequences in parallel computational mode.

The KLM control was first designed at the initial stage for analysis and simulation, it was then modified as an integrated controller with the three basic steps to detect facial features and emotion recognition, Figure 4 shows the index pages of the controller that imports a video sequence in real-time for feature extraction and detection. The final stages in the module detect the facial expression and the corresponding mood. One of the contributions of this paper is the configuration of unified control systems that automatically track faces in a video sequence and predict the mood of the person from cascaded feature points. The following section discusses some of the results from the test runs.

3 RESULT

Figure 5 shows a detected face with a default neutral expression. One of the limitations of the model is its inability to recognise multiple faces in a series of the video frame, only when each frame is rendered static; this process enables the programs to examine the sentiments of a person's face by utilising the sophisticated facial image dispensation the control model has to offer. The method generally analyses the procedures by using webcams to detect faces and capture expressions as default and in real-time human responses and movements in every position. This technique can be used to recognise emotion and understand how candidates feel during exercises like interviews and to measure how the candidates would react to certain questions online. The process can also be used to optimise the interview structure for future candidates would streamline the application procedures. Attention measure can be set by using the sliders to set background and foreground changes for attention measure with head and body orientation and pose.

The control is also designed to trace each facial expression that a person displays which is caused by facial muscles that move and contract differently and also makes the process easier for the KLM controller to capture emotion easier. These captured regions are encapsulated by the cascaded markers that move in motion to the facial muscles (Figure 6) and can be widespread de-

Figure 1: The four basic emotions that can be expressed by a person in an emotion detection study.

Figure 2: Optimisation of predicted feature parameters with Kalman filter.

pending on the emotion demonstrated on the face. The control can detect the five (5) emotions anonymously in real-time, by training the diverse datasets that help to make facial expression analysis more accurate. When a particular emotion is detected a confidence score is provided with its timestamp and the processed data is then aggregated and viewed on the visualisation dashboard as video output with detect facial expressions in real-time for ease and convenience. The controller can also determine an emotional expression based on several factors such as the location of the eyes, eyebrows, and mouth position. The model is capable of detecting eight emotions such as fear, happiness, neutral, sad, anger, surprise, disgust, and contempt. Each expression is sharpened according to the facial image (Figure 6).

In some aspects of the analysis, issues were found when trying to open the webcam from the port camera and asserted failed messages are often registered, these error messages happen if the camera is not properly enabled during program installation and hence the camera drivers are not properly installed. This can also be corrected by a predefined command that holds all error calls and automates start. One of the most basic tasks in face recognition is face detection which can automatically render a video sequence static and also in real-time

Figure 3: Framework for feature point tracking on video sequence to detect emotion.

capture for multiple faces. The most common way to detect this is the cascade classifier of the KLM controller. Face detection using the KLM controller can also be a bit tricky when it comes to classifying disgust to anger, these expressions are characterised by bared teeth with only a slight twist to the disgust expression.

Also, a smile and happy expression can be characterised by straight curved lips and bared teeth (Figures 7c and 7d), and each can be identified and detected by the number of cascaded points on the region of each feature. A total of three thousand markers can be used to detect a default expression in static mode any feedback less than that is mapped to an assigned expression from the list of mapped features in the database (Table 1). The module in the KLM controllers used the code value to assign each expression on the face that matches the one contained in the database.

Error measure for bi-directional tracking is also calcu-

Figure 4: Index page of the KLM controller with basic controls for emotion detection on the video sequence.

Figure 5: Single face detected from the video sequence with a default expression at the static point.

lated based on aggregate, Figure 8 shows the bi-directional tracking for the feature points, the model can automatically detect the tracking failure by forward and backward tracking of the pixels, and the tracking error and tracking can be synchronously due similarity in KLM filter applications, the SGFilter is used as a baseline to determine the error that exceeds the maximum limit. The method is a valid point since it is based on both forward and backward trajectories and it is similar in both ways; for this particular case, an error rate of 0.15% is seen as a good tracking accuracy for the number of markers assigned as cascaded object detector of the controller. For

a more accurate result, all invalid and static pixels are removed and only valid pixels are selected to show the trajectories of the valid points in red and blue.

4 CONCLUSION

This paper set out to demonstrate real-time analytics for emotion recognition based on facial expression with inference Kalman filter, the tracking process makes use of three modules face detection, feature identification, face tracking, and detection. The program is signalled as a vision cascade object detector system to detect and

Figure 6: Captured facial image with cascaded markers on facial muscle movement and a static default expression as "Neutral".

Table 1: List of facial expressions and the characteristic features assigned with values to identify them.

Emotion	Characteristic features	Value
Anger	Bared teeth, wrinkled eyes	2
Happy	Bared teeth, wrinkled eyes, straight lips	3
Smile	Curved lips up, wrinkled eyes	1
Fear	Round eyes, open mouth	5
Sad	Curved lips down	4
Disgust	Bared teeth twisted, sleet eyes	6
Surprise	Open wide eyes and mouth	7

locate a face from a video sequence; the detector object uses the KLM inference that trains the classification model for detection. The module can also be used to track moving objects with distinct features. The originality of the process is that all vision point tracker works as a window-based control system. The system is also embedded with error detection and tracking points, with a frequency of 10Hz from every facial angle, and can be used to track even the most subtle point of a blurred image at an estimated geometric transform. One of its limitations is that two different facial expressions could produce a similar effect and this is rectified by assigning a single numerical value to the assigned characteristic. The future perspective would be to compare tracking with other standard models like the multi-tracking convolutional neural network and Support vector machine for tracking speed.

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Figure 7: Real-time detection of the emotional response of a user

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Figure 8: Bi-directional error tracking face detected based on aggregate measures.

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